

THE ROLE OF THE SHANGHAI COOPERATION ORGANIZATION AS AN INTERNATIONAL LEGAL MECHANISM FOR PEACE AND SECURITY IN AFGHANISTAN

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ABSTRACT

this thesis assesses the international legal mechanisms for peace and security, the role of regional organizations, in particular the SCO, as an international legal mechanism in ensuring peace and security in Afghanistan.

International legal mechanisms include the settlement of various disputes and conflicts that may arise within the framework of international law, peace and international security, respect for human rights, human security, the creation of a favorable interstate trade and economic environment, the prevention of environmental problems and understands the generally accepted means of international law in the rapid solution of existing environmental problems, the fight against drugs, the prevention and elimination of the threat of terrorism.

These mechanisms can be created in general before the conflict that needs to be resolved, or in the aftermath of the conflict, in order to resolve the conflict.

As subjects of international legal mechanisms, we can first of all mention the states, as well as international organizations. In addition, regional organizations can be subjects of international legal mechanisms.

The ongoing unrest in the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan for several years, the

weakness of the central government, the fact that the country is in fact divided into two parts are affecting other countries, not only in Central Asia, but in the whole world. It is no secret to any of us that it poses a threat of terrorism and drug abuse.

Efforts by international organizations and states to resolve the current unrest in the country have yielded, at least in part, the expected results, as a result of the recent talks between the Afghan government and Taliban leaders in Doha, Qatar. We have to admit that the United States and the Taliban have reached an agreement¹.

However, the current situation requires the world community not only to unite, but also to create new and effective mechanisms to ensure peace and security.

Speaking at the SCO summit in November 2020, President Mirziyoyev said that "today it is more important than ever to

¹<https://www.reuters.com/article/us-usa-afghanistan-taliban/u-s-taliban-sign-historic-troop-withdrawal-deal-in-doha-idUSKBN20N06R>

miss the historic opportunity to achieve the long-awaited peace in Afghanistan"².

Indeed, it is important to note that this is a good time to reconcile the parties to the conflict. Because now both sides want to take the talks to a new level.

Enhancing the role of not only international organizations but also regional organizations in the conduct and effective conclusion of these negotiations will play an important role in peace and security efforts. In particular, the greater involvement of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, which is strengthening its position day by day, in the work of ensuring peace and security in Afghanistan may be crucial in overcoming the existing problem. In particular, the accession of India and Pakistan to the organization has further expanded the capabilities of the SCO³.

We know that the main goals of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization are to further develop trade and economic cooperation between member states, as well as to combat terrorism, religious extremism and separatism in the field of security, and to strengthen regional security and stability⁴. The organization is working to improve its operations.

The next meeting of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) Council of Heads of State in the form of a video conference in 2020 also discussed issues of

further strengthening multifaceted cooperation within the SCO in the face of new global threats and challenges.

In his speech at the summit, President Mirziyoyev stressed that the Shanghai Cooperation Organization is at a fundamentally new stage of development, and stressed that the fight against terrorism, extremism and drug trafficking should be in the focus of the SCO. The President of Uzbekistan also called on the summit participants to support the peace process in Afghanistan and the country's involvement in regional trade and economic ties.

In this regard, the SCO-Afghanistan Dialogue Group proposed to adopt a plan of practical measures to promote the socio-economic recovery of Afghanistan as soon as possible. Particular attention was paid to initiatives to build transport corridors to Afghanistan that would restore its historic role as a bridge connecting Central and South Asia⁵.

These initiatives will require further reform of the SCO, increasing its role in ensuring peace and international security.

Today, the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan is an observer in the SCO. President Ashraf Ghani has also been active in the SCO, endorsing his focus on resolving the situation in Afghanistan. In general, the international community, recognizing the growing role of the SCO, is interested in its involvement in international relations as a mechanism for peace and security.

Therefore, in the future to ensure the SCO's economic and social assistance to Afghanistan, to improve the activities of the Regional Anti-Terrorist Structure, which is an important body of the organization, to establish a special unit on Afghanistan within

²<https://xs.uz/uz/post/ozbekiston-respublikasi-prezidenti-shavkat-mirziyoevning-shankhaj-hamkorlik-tashkiloti-sammitidagi-nutqi>

³ На саммите ШОС утверждено решение о принятии в состав организации Индии и Пакистана // Официальный сайт телеканала Russia Today. Режим доступа: <https://russian.rt.com/article/102646#top> (дата обращения: 10.09.2015).

⁴ Шанхайская конвенция о борьбе с терроризмом, сепаратизмом и экстремизмом. Официальный сайт Министерства иностранных дел Российской Федерации. Режим доступа: http://www.mid.ru/foreign_policy/international_safety/crime/asset_publisher/3F51ZsLVsX4R/content/id/579622 (дата обращения: 18.10.2016).

⁵ <https://uzlidep.uz/uz/news-of-uzbekistan/7610>

this structure, to join the SCO. It is necessary to organize a peace conference with the participation of states and officials of the Afghan government and the Taliban, on the basis of which it is necessary to adopt a legal document outlining mutual commitments. The international legal framework of the SCO will include clear legal obligations of the parties,

clauses on mutual assistance, and effective ways to ensure peace and security in the region. The implementation of these actions can play an important role in improving international legal mechanisms to ensure peace and security in the region.

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